

CLASSIFICATION OF INFORMATION EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES AND COMPUTER TRAINING SOFTWARE

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Abstract: The classification of information technologies is considered, their use in education is analyzed.

Keywords: information, technology, information technology, education, presentation of educational information, knowledge testing, computer information technologies.

The relevance of the topic under consideration is supported by the constant development and emergence of new computer and telecommunication tools, electronic educational resources, the intensive expansion of illustrative and interactive capabilities, the quality and effectiveness of computer training software, distance self-learning, and automated knowledge control. The subject content of the educational environment today occurs both through the development and use of traditional educational resources (books, audiovisual materials, etc.), and through the introduction of modern and promising electronic educational resources and software tools built and used on the basis of advanced computer technology and new information technologies.

The main elements of the educational environment are teachers, learners, educational resources and software, computers and networking tools, consumer electronics and other teaching aids.

The modern educational environment should provide support for various types and forms of educational activities, which include:

1. training (full-time, part-time, distance learning);
2. self-study (self-education) - is carried out on one or more topics or disciplines without the participation of teachers, using a computer connected to the Internet ;
3. advanced training or retraining - usually carried out on a full-time basis,

according to a special program.

All known educational resources can be divided into the following groups:

1. Traditional printed publications and methodological materials, including text, tables and graphic illustrations: textbooks and teaching aids, texts and lecture notes, laboratory workshops, problem books, encyclopedias, reference books, atlases, maps, diagrams, albums, catalogs and lists, guidebooks, dictionaries (explanatory, terminological, etc.), reading books, handouts and demonstration materials, templates and forms to fill out, methodological guides and developments for certain types of training sessions.

2. Traditional (analog) audiovisual materials and products: musical materials, speech materials, special sounds and effects, video films, demos, presentation fragments, cinematographic products.

3. Modern (digital) electronic educational resources. They are files or various media containing traditional resources from groups 1-2, which can be played for viewing and/or listening on devices of modern (digital) consumer electronics and/or computer technology.

4. Software for computer learning, as well as self-learning, self-education and control of acquired knowledge - programs, software systems or software systems and environments designed to solve certain pedagogical problems, having subject content and focused on interaction with the student .

In addition, electronic educational resources and computer learning software can be concentrated at the user (local) and network (remote / remote, distributed).

The generalized classification of electronic educational resources

naturally relies on all traditional printed and audiovisual resources that can be converted into electronic form, saved as files or media. They include:

- files (text documents with embedded tables and graphic illustrations, graphic illustration files) - file equivalents of traditional resources from group 1;
- HTML documents that include text, graphics, multimedia and hypermedia elements - electronic textbooks, tutorials, laboratory workshops

and other electronic equivalents of traditional resources from groups 1-2;

- CD - ROM , Audio - CD , Video - CD and other media of educational information;
- DVD -carriers of audiovisual educational information.

The classification of computer learning software is carried out according to the following criteria:

1. By the nature of the content (discipline): humanitarian, natural science, technical.
2. According to the pedagogical tasks to be solved (software equivalents of traditional resources from groups 1-2, providing the presentation of text, graphics, multimedia elements):
 - means of theoretical and technological training:
 - computer training programs - early computer training tools containing text and hypertext components, built-in static and / or programmed dynamic graphics;
 - computer (electronic) textbooks and manuals;
 - automated training modules - programs for visual support of the process of studying the most complex and important issues of academic disciplines and its control;
 - automated test control systems of knowledge - software tools that provide: for teachers - input and editing of lists of groups of students, sets of test tasks, answer options, grade points, as well as calculation and output of statistical data of individual and group testing in many disciplines; for trainees - the possibility of passing test control procedures, calculating the results and deriving control scores;
 - means of practical training:
 - computer problem books (workshops) and solution books - programs for supporting the visual environment for solving a certain class of problems using templates and forms for entering initial data, mathematical models and their graphical representations;
 - computer simulators - designed to develop the skills and abilities of a certain activity, as well as the development of related abilities;

- auxiliary means (contributing to the solution of problems of theoretical, technological or practical training, but in an independent capacity are not sufficient to achieve the corresponding goals):
 - computer encyclopedias - advanced software tools that provide multimedia support for a structured system of illustrated descriptions of a vast subject area being studied;
 - computer directories, atlases, maps, diagrams, albums, catalogs and lists of objects under study - software tools that provide textual and graphic support for systematization, viewing and analysis of the characteristics and properties of objects under study;
 - computer guides to the studied objects;
 - computer terminological dictionaries, as well as explanatory and other - software tools that provide structuring, input, editing and viewing of terms or materials of articles and illustrations;
 - multimedia training sessions - means, the main content of which is a multimedia recording of a real training session or event (lecture, seminar, demonstration);
 - complex tools (covering a wide range of pedagogical tasks):
 - automated (or computer) training courses - software for automated support of various types of training sessions in the discipline; they integrate functions or means for solving the main problems of theoretical, technological and practical training.
 - There are also other types of complex tools that combine tools of different types, or implement the functions inherent in them. Such tools include, for example, training and training systems, professional certification systems, etc.
3. By level of education: for school education, for primary and secondary vocational education, for higher vocational education, for vocational training and advanced training in sectoral educational systems.
4. According to the forms of information presentation: multimedia , non-multimedia.

In the presented classification of educational resources, an attempt was made to combine and develop known similar classifications. The classification reflects the state of development of electronic educational resources and computer educational technologies of today and takes into account many of the main trends in their development. In the considered classification, almost all important objects of modern educational technologies are positioned quite accurately, for example, electronic and computer textbooks, automated training courses, training modules and systems.

Literature:

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